

Genetic variability in photosynthesis and chlorophyll content of various landraces of upland rice

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After an extensive survey of the Kumaun region in the Central Himalaya, 28 different landraces of upland rice were collected. These landraces were studied for variation in chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate and were compared with an introduced high-yielding variety (VL 206) released by the Vivekananda Hill Agriculture Research Laboratory, Almora (Indian Council of Agricultural Research), for rainfed areas.

Landraces were grown in earthen pots (30 cm diameter and 30 cm high) containing farmyard manure, sand, and soil

(1:1:1, v/v) during kharif (wet season) in 1998. Three sets of plants (15 plants per set) per landrace were kept under similar environmental conditions in the Institute nursery at Kosi (1,150 m asl; geographical coordinates 79°38' 10" E and 29°38' 15" N). Pots were irrigated to maintain soil moisture (around 23–25%) for seed germination. No watering was done after germination and plants were kept under rainfed conditions.

Observations were made before the flowering stage (90 ± 5 d after seed sowing). Optimum photosynthetic activities

during this stage have been noted (Chauhan et al 1996). The photosynthesis rate was measured in flag leaves of three uniform plants from each set, using a closed portable photosynthetic system model LI-6400 (LI-COR, USA). Measurements were carried out at 25 °C and at 800 mmol m⁻² s⁻¹ to avoid possible fluctuations due to temperature and light variations. The chlorophyll contents (chlorophyll a & b and total) of the flag leaves of various landraces were estimated following the method of Holm (1954).

Photosynthesis, stomatal conductance, and chlorophyll content of various landraces of rice (±SD).

Landrace/ introduced variety	Net photosynthesis (mmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	Stomatal conductance (mmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	Chlorophyll (mg g ⁻¹)		
			a	b	Total
<i>Landraces</i>					
Anjani	2.21 ± 0.12	34.80 ± 3.91	0.591 ± 0.062	0.253 ± 0.030	0.843 ± 0.090
Bauran	4.70 ± 0.50	127.20 ± 12.60	0.662 ± 0.194	0.259 ± 0.061	0.922 ± 0.255
Bauriya	4.80 ± 0.03	73.50 ± 1.26	0.707 ± 0.174	0.324 ± 0.067	1.031 ± 0.240
Bindudhan	2.53 ± 0.57	5.30 ± 5.80	0.338 ± 0.046	0.146 ± 0.146	0.484 ± 0.066
Chhatuli	2.61 ± 0.47	53.91 ± 2.76	0.614 ± 0.151	0.234 ± 0.051	0.848 ± 0.202
Chhotiya	2.27 ± 0.15	32.60 ± 2.30	0.504 ± 0.143	0.217 ± 0.057	0.723 ± 0.199
Dalbadal	3.12 ± 0.50	67.70 ± 4.00	0.826 ± 0.202	0.313 ± 0.075	1.139 ± 0.277
Danbasmati	3.35 ± 0.46	66.70 ± 1.30	0.879 ± 0.153	0.339 ± 0.054	1.218 ± 0.207
Dehradonibasmati	2.60 ± 0.41	56.71 ± 3.50	0.583 ± 0.061	0.256 ± 0.015	0.839 ± 0.062
Dudhikapkoti	3.76 ± 0.44	72.70 ± 5.48	0.702 ± 0.030	0.136 ± 0.018	0.838 ± 0.049
Dutiau	2.44 ± 0.38	50.20 ± 2.81	0.336 ± 0.057	0.140 ± 0.012	0.476 ± 0.070
Jhungia	2.46 ± 0.36	63.11 ± 2.82	0.913 ± 0.145	0.452 ± 0.063	1.365 ± 0.202
Kaladur	2.60 ± 0.55	88.81 ± 4.94	0.850 ± 0.024	0.411 ± 0.031	1.261 ± 0.044
Kaunkaun	2.30 ± 0.24	45.20 ± 2.87	1.060 ± 0.279	0.400 ± 0.095	1.460 ± 0.374
Khudinandhani	2.26 ± 0.08	43.40 ± 2.00	0.683 ± 0.050	0.282 ± 0.007	0.965 ± 0.058
Kururhidhan	2.73 ± 0.70	65.60 ± 2.98	0.500 ± 0.120	0.208 ± 0.045	0.708 ± 0.165
Laldhan	4.58 ± 0.39	116.00 ± 2.34	0.549 ± 0.107	0.229 ± 0.044	0.778 ± 0.152
Nandhani	2.42 ± 0.47	53.00 ± 2.60	0.638 ± 0.258	0.173 ± 0.200	0.811 ± 0.112
Nauli	5.37 ± 0.45	122.80 ± 4.10	1.264 ± 0.040	0.281 ± 0.031	1.545 ± 0.070
Patoli	4.15 ± 0.41	78.00 ± 1.80	0.878 ± 0.068	0.189 ± 0.025	1.061 ± 0.138
Sabhawati	3.18 ± 0.41	59.81 ± 2.61	0.640 ± 0.078	0.352 ± 0.065	1.082 ± 0.064
Sailani	5.27 ± 0.28	136.80 ± 10.70	0.896 ± 0.115	0.242 ± 0.045	1.138 ± 0.161
Santoli	2.36 ± 0.12	68.51 ± 5.01	0.840 ± 0.103	0.254 ± 0.086	1.095 ± 0.173
Saunji	3.64 ± 0.44	116.50 ± 8.03	0.502 ± 0.178	0.214 ± 0.060	0.716 ± 0.238
Saurajubawan	8.10 ± 0.58	122.00 ± 6.07	1.133 ± 0.110	0.212 ± 0.031	1.320 ± 0.142
Syaudhan	6.30 ± 0.40	149.00 ± 10.46	0.678 ± 0.091	0.335 ± 0.032	1.014 ± 0.119
Taichin	9.45 ± 0.44	230.50 ± 13.90	1.325 ± 0.123	0.231 ± 0.056	1.556 ± 0.179
Tilansi	2.29 ± 0.45	71.10 ± 4.90	0.731 ± 0.108	0.314 ± 0.056	1.046 ± 0.165
<i>Introduced variety</i>					
VL 206	7.22 ± 0.90	161.10 ± 2.34	0.836 ± 0.154	0.384 ± 0.137	1.220 ± 0.275

Data on photosynthesis (see table) reveal that various landraces differed significantly in photosynthetic rates (CO_2 uptake ranged from 2.21 to 9.45 $\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and stomatal conductance (between 34.8 and 230.5 $\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The leaf chlorophyll content also showed significant variation among different landraces: chlorophyll a = 0.336–1.325, chlorophyll b = 0.136–0.452, and total chlorophyll = 0.476–1.556 mg g^{-1} of fresh weight.

Several landraces (18% of total) exhibited high photosynthetic rate (CO_2 uptake $>5 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Total chlorophyll content was also greater (1.338–1.556 mg g^{-1}) in these landraces; 32% of the landraces could be placed in an intermediate group for which CO_2 uptake ranged between 3 and 5 $\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. For this intermediate group, total chlorophyll

content ranged from 0.716 to 1.218 mg g^{-1} . Half of the landraces showed low photosynthesis (CO_2 uptake $<3 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). A similar trend was seen for stomatal conductance in the landraces. Introduced variety VL 206 exhibited physiological characteristics (photosynthesis, stomatal conductance, and chlorophyll content) similar to those of landraces with high photosynthesis.

The rate of photosynthetic CO_2 uptake is an important component of plant growth (Leding and Botkin 1974). Our results indicate a positive correlation of net photosynthesis with stomatal conductance ($P < 0.01$) and chlorophyll content ($P < 0.02$). These characteristics can thus be used for the primary selection of appropriate landraces for a particular environment. Further, these landraces can serve as donors of genes for introgressing

from landraces with high photosynthesis to those with low photosynthesis through suitable genetic approaches.

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Digital Literacy for Rice Scientists

To help rice scientists take advantage of new information and communication technologies, the IRRI Training Center has developed the *Digital Literacy Course for Rice Scientists*. The course aims to provide scientists with information about what resources are available on the Internet and how they can go about accessing these resources.

The course is unique in that it focuses on the needs of rice scientists, it provides a forum for rice scientists to share their experiences and Internet resources with other rice scientists online, and it establishes a learner-centered knowledge network in the form of an online community centered on rice research.

The topics covered by the course include

- What is the Internet
- What is the World Wide Web and what makes it work
- Key Internet terminology
- How to use the Internet for communication with other scientists
- How to use Web browsers
- How to search for information efficiently and effectively
- What are some of the good sources of information for rice scientists available on the Internet
- How to cite Internet documents
- What training opportunities are available online

Connection to the Internet offers national scientists a low-cost communication medium with other scientists linked to the Internet, gives them access to the ever-growing body of information available on and through interlinked computers throughout the world, and provides access to formal and informal training offered online from virtually anywhere.

